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STRAIGHTNESS ANALYSIS OF MACHINE TOOL WITH NON-LINEAR KINEMATICS

Abstract: Straightness of the machine tool affects the accuracy of the workpiece to a great extent. Using well-established technics the straightness of linear axis of the machine tools can be determined with a high accuracy. Machine tools with non-linear kinematics are much different in relation to the machine tools with serial mechanisms. It is necessary to be sure that the existing procedures are appropriate for determining the straightness of machine tools with non-linear kinematics. For that purpose the straightness accuracy of linear axis of a machine tool with so-called O-X glide parallel mechanism, which has non-linear kinematic characteristics, is determined through laser displacement measurements.

Key words: Straightness, machine tool, non-linear kinematics, O-X glide

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of the workpiece is affected by the accuracy of the machine tool (MT) to a great extent. The accuracy of the MT depends on a big variety of factors and so the MT errors can be classified in main groups. These groups according to [1] are geometric and kinematic errors, thermal errors, cutting force induced errors, fixturing errors and controller errors. The geometric and kinematic errors have a big impact on the production process and on the workpiece quality, thus it is necessary to be aware with the momentary status of the MT.

Through MT validation the effect of these errors can be reduced. Geometric validation tests measure the MT accuracy and repeatability with series of simple positioning tests, generally operating under no-load conditions. The results of these tests are positioning accuracy, straightness, squareness and parallelism of the linear axes, the concentricity of the rotary axes, etc. [2].

One of the main characteristics of MT is the workspace and the analysis of the workspace is one of the basic elements used for machine development. The workspace of conventional mechanisms with serial or linear kinematics differs greatly from parallel kinematic structure mechanisms with non-linear kinematics [3]. By applying parallel mechanisms in the construction of the mechanical structure of machine tools, a workspace with a complex geometric shape and reduced volume is obtained compared to conventional machine tools. This initiated the realization of a large number of researches in the field of workspace analysis [4–6], with the aim of determining the applicability of parallel mechanisms in machine tools from this point of view. As a result of those researches, in order to overcome certain shortcomings of parallel mechanisms, a larger group of mechanisms with combined, series-parallel, or hybrid kinematics appeared [7–9].

The non-linearity of the MT can also be described by the resolution of the MT. The resolution of the MT mechanism can be seen as the possible displacement of the platform of the mechanism. In MT with serial

kinematics, the resolution is equal to the minimum change of internal coordinates Δp and it is valid for every point of the working space $\Delta p = \Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z$, while in mechanisms with parallel kinematics, this is not valid due to their constructions, geometry and methods work. By changing one of the internal coordinates of the parallel mechanism, the platform will not move in the direction of the internal coordinate change, and the displacement values are different $\Delta p \neq \Delta x \neq \Delta y \neq \Delta z$ [10].

Due to the existence of this type of nonlinear property of MT with a parallel mechanism, they are also called machine tools with nonlinear kinematics (MTNK) [11].

In the work the straightness of three linear axis X, Y and Z is measured in all perpendicular directions with a laser straightness interferometer measuring system.

2. STRAIGHTNESS MEASUREMENT OF MACHINE TOOLS

The definition of straightness error of the linear axis according to ISO 230-1 [12], is the value of the largest positive straightness deviation added to the absolute value of the largest negative straightness deviation with respect to any previously defined reference straight line. There are three types of defining the reference line:

- Mean minimum zone reference straight line;
- Least square reference straight line;
- End-point reference straight line.

Fig. 1. shows the end-point reference straight line. It is the most common method to express the straightness error of a linear axis. In the figure a and b are the end points, l is the straight reference line, 2 is the biggest positive deviation of the reference straight line, 3 is the biggest negative deviation of the reference straight line and 4 is the measured deviation of the straightness.

Straightness measurements can be performed using various methods: straightedge and linear displacement sensor, microscope and taut wire, alignment telescope, alignment laser, and laser straightness interferometry.

Fig. 1. End-point reference straight line for an imaginary Z-axis in direction of X-axis [12]

The development of a system, by which the 2D motion errors of the linear axes of the MT can be measured at the same time using the direction regulation of the laser interferometer, is performed by [13]. According to this procedure, the positioning accuracy, straightness and flatness of individual linear axes can be checked at the same time.

Fig. 2 shows the principles of the laser straightness interferometry. Laser beam goes through the interferometer, also referred to as a Wollaston prism, the laser beam splits in two parts due to the two initial frequencies (double frequency laser beam f_1, f_2) by a small angle θ . The two laser beams arrive to the reflector, and reflect back to the interferometer. Inside the interferometer the recombination of the beams creates a new beam which heads back to the sensor of the laser head. Relative displacement of the axis (Δx) of the prism causes changes in the recombination of the reflected laser beams, thus using this principle the deviation from the initial straight line can be measured.

The orientation of the reflector defines if the measurement of the displacement is performed in the horizontal or vertical plane.

Fig. 2. Principles of the laser straightness interferometry [14]

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Straightness measurements are performed on a MT with hybrid (serial-parallel) mechanism, which has non-linear kinematics. The movement in X-Z plane is realized with so-called O-X glide mechanism [15,16] and the movement in the Y axis with a serial mechanism. In Fig. 3 the O-X glide mechanism is shown and in Fig. 4 the experimental setup for measuring the straightness error of linear axes of the machine tool is shown.

The movements along the Y-axis are performed using the serial mechanism and it has a purely linear kinematic characteristic. Movements along the Z-axis are performed using the parallel mechanism and it has a non-linear kinematic characteristic. On the other hand, the movements along the X-axis are performed using the parallel mechanism, but it has a linear kinematic characteristic, which is variable along the Z axis. It is the reason why the X-axis has quasi-linear kinematic characteristics.

Fig. 3. The O-X glide mechanism [16]

Fig. 4. The experimental setup on the O-X glide for measuring the X-axis in perpendicular Z-axis

The straightness measurements are conducted in bi-directional way, which refers to a series of measurements in which the approach to a target position is always made in either directions along the axis [17]. The two directions are called positive and negative. Positive movement direction means movement along an axis in positive, increasing coordinates and negative is the opposite.

4. RESULTS OF THE STRAIGHTNESS MEASUREMENTS

After conducting the measurements for all three linear axes (X, Y and Z) in two perpendicular planes (X-Y, X-Z, Y-X, Y-Z, Z-X and Z-Y) the data of straightness of the linear axis is obtained. In Fig. 5-10 the results of measurements in two normal planes for each axis are graphically illustrated. The end-point reference straight line method is used to show the acquired values.

Fig. 5. Straightness error of X-axis in Y direction

Fig. 6. Straightness error of X-axis in Z direction

Fig. 7. Straightness error of Y-axis in X direction

Fig. 8. Straightness error of Y-axis in Z direction

Fig. 9. Straightness error of Z-axis in X direction

Fig. 10. Straightness error of Z-axis in Y direction

Table 1 shows the maximum positive and maximum negative values of the measured straightness's for every axis from both positive and negative movement directions. Values obtained for X axis are in optimal range, the absolute values under $50 \mu\text{m}$ according to [17]. Values obtained for Y-axis in perpendicular X-axis are also under $50 \mu\text{m}$, thus acceptable. On the other hand the Z-axis in both perpendicular X and Y axis and also Y-axis in perpendicular Z-axis are over the acceptable limit.

Main axis	Perpend. axis	Straightness displacement [μm]	
		Max. positive	Max. negative
X	Y	0	-21,97
	Z	7,36	-28,45
Y	X	22,79	-45,29
	Z	142,96	0
Z	X	11,63	-75,22
	Y	297,23	0

Table 1. Straightness errors of the axis

5. DISCUSSION

After analyzing the obtained values about the straightness error of all three axis, the next conclusions can be drawn:

- The quasi-linear X-axis has the best straightness characteristics of all axis.
- The linear Y axis is worse than the X axis but better than the Z axis.
- The Z-axis, which has non-linear characteristics is the worst. In both X and Y perpendicular directions the values of straightness deviation are above the acceptable $50 \mu\text{m}$ limit.

The parallel mechanism is constructed from rods with changeable length. The rods are put together from 3 (the shorter rods) and from 4 (the longer rods) separate subparts with threads on them. Length of the rods can be changed tightening or loosening up the previously mentioned threads. During the construction of the MT the length of these rods are fixed, calibrated and precisely measured, because it plays an important role in the definition of machine tool internal kinematics.

The straightness error of Y axis in positive movement direction is greater, then the straightness error in negative movement direction.

The straightness error of X axis in perpendicular Y direction is greater in the negative movement direction then in positive, but the straightness error of X axis in perpendicular Z direction is greater in the positive movement direction then in negative in major part of the movement path of the linear axis.

The straightness error of the Z axis can be divided in two parts:

- The part within coordinates from -60 to -40 mm – lower subpart of the movement path.
- The part within coordinates from -40 to -15 mm – upper subpart of the movement path.

The -40mm coordinate is a transition point, where the significance of the positive movement direction decreases and the negative movement direction increases, or vice versa. For the perpendicular X direction the straightness error of Z axis is greater in positive movement direction at the upper subpart, but in the lower subpart the negative movement direction has a greater significance.

On the other hand, for the perpendicular Y direction the straightness error of Z axis is greater in positive movement direction in the lower subpart of the movement path, but in the upper subpart the negative movement direction has a greater significance.

Bi-directional straightness error of all three linear

axis follows the trend of the straightness errors of both unidirectional movement directions.

6. CONCLUSION

The straightness measurements of all three linear axis's were conducted using the laser straightness interferometry method, to obtain the necessary straightness deviation values. They provide good insight in the current condition of the machine tool with O-X glide parallel mechanism. The X-axis has not to big issues, but the Y and mainly the Z axis is in very poor condition. Further investigation for finding the reasons of this state of the axis are necessary. However, the Y and Z axes have significantly larger straightness deviations. The main reason for this is that the testing was done on a prototype primarily intended to check kinematic characteristics and control algorithms. A possible reason for deviations could be the characteristics of the joints and errors in the internal kinematic equations. Because the control of the MT is out of sync with the real position of the platform.

7. REFERENCES

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